

Analysis of Psychosocial Risk Factors Affecting Job Performance of Personnel at a Financial Institution

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ABSTRACT

A descriptive and cross-sectional study was conducted in a financial institution in Tulcán, Ecuador, involving 86 employees from the operational and administrative areas. The Psychosocial Assessment Questionnaire in Workspaces from the Ministry of Labor and the Individual Work Performance Questionnaire (IPWQ) by Koopmans were used. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 26, applying statistical tests such as Odds Ratio and Chi². 80% of employees perceived a low psychosocial risk in the overall evaluation. Regarding work organization, 89% reported low risk, 31% reported medium risk concerning workload and work pace; 37% perceived medium risk in the scope of action and control, and 24% indicated insufficient rest periods. Additionally, 22% perceived a medium risk in leadership. In terms of job performance, 91% showed high task performance, and 77% exhibited low levels of counterproductive behaviors. The Chi² test revealed significant relationships between psychosocial factors and job performance, highlighting scope of action and control (OR=125), leadership (OR=42), and recovery (OR=70.2) as the most influential factors. Psychosocial factors have a significant impact on job performance. Effective leadership and proper work organization are essential to promote a favorable work environment, improving productivity and reducing risks associated with stress and mental health.

Keywords: psychosocial factors; occupational risks; job performance; work environment; financial institution.

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Introduction

In recent decades, psychosocial factors have gained relevance in the workplace due to their significant influence on the well-being and performance of workers, especially in the financial work environment characterized by high demands, low wages, and the need to maintain productivity in a competitive market, which increases employees' exposure to psychosocial risks (1).

Psychosocial risk factors refer to the interactions between the work environment, job characteristics, organizational aspects, and the needs and capabilities of worker (2). These interactions can negatively impact the mental and physical health of employees, resulting in issues such as stress, emotional exhaustion, demotivation, and consequently, a decrease in work performance (3).

The International Labor Organization (ILO) and the World Health Organization (WHO) have highlighted the importance of addressing psychosocial risk factors in workplaces, emphasizing that these can affect employees' personal satisfaction both inside and outside of work (4). In Ecuador, labor legislation includes specific provisions for the protection of workers exposed to these risks. However, despite regulatory efforts, employees continue to face significant challenges related to these factors, leading to an increase in mental health issues and a decline in work performance across various industries, including finance (5).

Among the most common psychosocial risk factors in financial institutions are workload overload, lack of control over assigned tasks, pressure to meet demanding goals, and managing complex interpersonal relationships with both colleagues and clients, which contribute to

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increased work-related stress, leading to problems such as depression, anxiety, and other stress-related disorders (6).

The impact of psychosocial risk factors is not limited to the individual level; it also has significant organizational and economic repercussions. Workers experiencing high levels of stress often show a decrease in their ability to concentrate, make decisions, and maintain consistent performance, which in turn translates into lower productivity, higher absenteeism, and an increase in work errors (7).

In 2020, Ríos conducted a study identifying several psychosocial risk factors affecting work performance in various Ecuadorian companies, evidencing the relationship between lack of clarity in job functions and increased fatigue and stress among employees. It revealed that the lack of support from supervisors and coworkers increases the risk of developing mental health issues, negatively impacting work performance (8).

Based on the aforementioned background, the objective of this study is to identify the psychosocial risk factors that affect the work performance of employees in a financial institution, which will serve as a foundation for the implementation of strategies that promote their well-being and improve their work performance.

Methodology

This study is framed within a descriptive, cross-sectional, and quantitative research design, following the methodological guidelines proposed by Hernández et al. (9).

The study population consisted of 86 workers from a financial institution, including both operational and administrative staff. Due to the size of the population, it was decided to include all workers in the study, thereby eliminating the need for sampling techniques and ensuring the representativeness of the results. This choice allows for a comprehensive view of employees' perceptions and experiences regarding psychosocial risks in their work environment.

For participant selection, the following criteria were used:

Inclusion criteria: Employees from the operational and administrative areas of the financial institution in Tulcán, Ecuador, who agree to participate in the research and sign the informed consent.

Exclusion criteria: Employees who do not agree

to be part of the research and do not sign the informed consent, or who are on vacation leave.

For data collection, the Psychosocial Risk Assessment Questionnaire in Workspaces from the Ministry of work of Ecuador (10), was used. This validated tool allows for the measurement of psychosocial risk factors through 58 questions distributed across 8 key dimensions, such as workload, control over tasks, social support, role clarity, among others. Responses are recorded on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree), facilitating the quantification of workers' perceptions regarding psychosocial risk factors.

To measure the dependent variable, the Individual Work Performance Questionnaire (IPWQ) (11), was utilized, an instrument designed to evaluate work performance across three dimensions: task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior, consisting of 18 items that provide a concise and self-reported assessment of employees' performance in their job.

Prior to data collection through the survey, awareness was raised about the importance of truthful responses to avoid biases and improve the understanding of the questions. Clarifications were provided regarding the meaning of each item and the response format to ensure that the data obtained accurately reflect employees' perceptions of psychosocial risk factors. Each worker then completed the questionnaires in a self-administered way.

The data obtained from the questionnaires were entered into a database using Microsoft Excel software and subsequently processed using SPSS statistical

software (version 25). Absolute and relative frequencies were employed for the descriptive analysis of the data, allowing for the identification of general patterns and trends in workers' responses. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test was conducted, observing that the data did not meet the normality assumptions; therefore, the non-parametric Chi-square test was used to verify the hypothesis.

The study complied with international ethical regulations, following the principles of the Helsinki Declaration (12), to ensure respect for the rights and well-being of participants. All employees who participated in the research signed an informed consent form, and it was explained that their participation was voluntary and confidential. Additionally, formal authorization was obtained from the legal representatives of the

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cooperative, who allowed access to the facilities and employees for conducting the surveys and carrying out the study without major interruptions.

Results

The study population consists of 87 individuals, of whom 59% were female. The age range of 35 to 43 years was the most predominant, accounting for 46%. All participants identified as mestizos. Regarding education level, 74% had tertiary education, while only 3% were employed with a high school diploma. In terms of work experience, 34% of employees have worked at the company for 3 to 10 years, with 67% working in the administrative area and 33% in operations (Table 1).

Table 1 Socio-demographic Information of Employees of the Financial Institution, 2024.

Variables	N	%
Sex		
Female	51	59%
Male	36	41%
Age		
16-24 years	7	8%
25-34 years	30	34%
35-43 years	40	46%
44-52 years	7	8%
≥ 53 years	3	3%
Ethnic Self-Identification		
Mixed race	87	100%
Education		
High School	3	3%
Technical/Technological	8	9%
Tertiary Level	64	74%
Fourth Level	12	14%
Work Experience		
≤ 2 years	29	33%
3 – 10 years	30	34%
11 – 20 years	24	28%
≥ 21 years	4	5%
Area		
Administrative	58	67%
Operational	29	33%

Source: Survey of Employees of the Financial Institution

Regarding psychosocial risk factors, most employees perceive a favorable work

environment, with 80% reporting low risk in the overall assessment. On the other hand, the work organization dimension stands out positively, with 89% at low risk, as well as competency development at 82% and support at 78%. However, the workload and pace indicate that 31% of employees experience medium risk. Similarly, in the action margin and control dimension, 37% of workers report medium risk; regarding recovery, 24% perceive medium risk, indicating potential insufficiencies in break times. Although the leadership dimension is predominantly positive with 76% at low risk, 22% of respondents evaluate it as medium risk (Table 2).

Table 2 Psychosocial Risk Factors

DIMENSIONS	Low Risk		Medium Risk		High Risk	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Dimension 1. Workload and Pace	59	68%	27	31%	1	1%
Dimension 2. Competency Development	71	82%	16	18%	0	0%
Dimension 3. Leadership	66	76%	19	22%	2	2%
Dimension 4. Action Margin and Control	55	63%	32	37%	0	0%
Dimension 5. Work Organization	77	89%	9	10%	1	1%
Dimension 6. Recovery	66	76%	21	24%	0	0%
Dimension 7. Support	68	78%	19	22%	0	0%
Dimension 8. Other Important Points	68	78%	19	22%	0	0%
Dimension 8.1 Discriminatory Harassment	66	76%	21	24%	0	0%
Dimension 8.2 Workplace Harassment	52	60%	26	30%	9	10%
Dimension 8.3 Sexual Harassment	70	80%	15	17%	2	2%
Dimension 8.4 Work Addiction	66	76%	21	24%	0	0%
Dimension 8.5 Work Conditions	58	67%	21	24%	8	9%
Dimension 8.6 Double Presence	62	71%	23	26%	2	2%
Dimension 8.7 Job and Emotional Stability	63	72%	23	26%	1	1%
Dimension 8.8 Self-perceived Health	59	68%	27	31%	1	1%
GLOBAL ASSESSMENT						
TOTAL RISK	70	80%	19	22%	0	0%

Source: Survey of Employees of the Financial Institution

Regarding job performance, in the task performance dimension, 91% of workers exhibit high performance; in the contextual performance, a more balanced distribution is observed, with 54% in high performance and 46% in moderate performance. Meanwhile, in counterproductive work behavior, which reflects behaviors that could negatively affect the work environment, 77% of employees show a low level of counterproductive behavior, while 11% are at each of the moderate and high levels. In the dimensions of other important points, workplace harassment had a high risk of 10%, followed by working conditions at 9%, making these the dimensions with the highest risk among all evaluated. In the overall assessment, 75% of workers have high performance, with 25% in moderate performance, and no workers with low performance, highlighting an efficient and productive work

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environment, although specific areas for improvement are identified (Table 3).

Table 3 Job Performance

DIMENSIONS	Low performance		Moderate Performance		High Performance	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Dimension 1. Task Performance	0	0%	8	9%	79	91%
Dimension 2. Contextual Performance	0	0%	40	46%	47	54%
Dimension 3. Counterproductive behavior	10	11%	10	11%	67	77%

Pace	1			41.9]
D2. Competency Development	11.6	<.00	6.9	[2.07, 23.0]
D3. Leadership	39.1	<.00	42	[9.64, 183]
D4. Margin of Action and Control	36.3	<.00	125*	[7.13, 2204]
D5. Work Organization	26.3	<.00	30.2	[5.53, 165]
D6. Recovery	35.1	<.00	70.2	[8.52, 578]
D7. Support and Assistance	9.7	.002	5.4	[1.74, 17.0]
D8. Other Important Points	64.7	<.00	357	[34.8, 3665]

TOTAL PERFORM

OVERALL ASSESSMENT

Source: Survey of Employees of the Financial

Institution

Overall Risk	.65	<.00	.575	[.149, 2.23]
	3	1		

^a Haldane-Anscombe correction applied

Table 4 shows a significant relationship between various psychosocial risk factors and the job performance of employees in a financial institution, with a p- value < .001. In particular, the margin of action and control has a considerable impact on job performance, with an Odds Ratio (OR) of 125 and a confidence interval (CI) ranging from 7.13 to 2204. Factors such as leadership (OR = 42), recovery (OR = 70.2), and work organization (OR = 30.2) also stand out as determining elements of good performance, evidencing that a well-organized work environment with effective leadership promotes high performance. Additionally, workload and pace (OR = 11.9) and competency development (OR = 6.89) moderately influence performance. The overall risk shows an OR of .575, suggesting that the probability of having low or moderate performance is lower if the work environment is mostly healthy.

Table 4 Psychosocial Risk Factors and Job Performance of Employees in the Financial Institution

WORK PERFORMANCE	Low, moderate, High Performance			
	X ²	p-value	Odds Ratio (OR)	OR 95%CI
D1. Workload and	19	<.00	11.9	[3.39,

OVERALL

PERFORMANC

E

D1. Workload and 19 <.00 11.9 [3.39,

Discussion

In the present study, the population distribution is balanced, with 59% women and 41% men, reflecting a trend similar to that observed in the research by Flores and Rodríguez (2020) in a banking institution in the city of Quito, where 60.9% of the employees were women and 39% were men (13).

Regarding age range, the predominant group is between 35 and 43 years old, with 46%, followed by the range of 25 to 34 years, with 34%. This is consistent with the results of the study conducted by Moreira and Vera (2023), in which 61.8% were in the age range of 36 to 45 years, while 17% were in the ranges of 26 to 35 years and 46 to 65 years, respectively (14).

In relation to psychosocial risk factors, leadership and work organization show a significant impact on job performance with high Odds Ratio values, consistent with the study conducted by Palacios et al. (2024), who also found that the quality of leadership is crucial for improving job performance (15).

On the other hand, the medium risk in workload and pace experienced by 31% of employees, and the 37% reporting medium risk in the margin of action and control dimension, align with the study by Delgado et al. (2020), which also documented the relationship between high job demands and decreased performance when employees do not have sufficient autonomy in decision-making (16).

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Finally, the significant relationship found between various psychosocial factors and job performance, with χ^2 values and $p < .001$, underscores the importance of properly managing these factors, as noted in the study by Freire and Corrales (2018), which mentions that “psychosocial risks have a considerable influence on job performance” (17). Similarly, Pilligua and Arteaga (2019) demonstrated that a lack of control or inadequate leadership can negatively influence occupational health and the overall well-being of workers, adversely impacting employee productivity (18).

Conclusion

The majority of workers perceive a favorable environment, with 80% reporting low risk in the overall evaluation of psychosocial factors, reflecting a positive environment that promotes workplace well-being. Dimensions such as work organization, competency development, and support have also been positively evaluated, suggesting that these aspects significantly contribute to maintaining high performance among most employees.

However, areas for improvement have been identified in dimensions such as workload and pace, where 31% of employees perceive medium risk, which could affect their ability to manage stress effectively. Additionally, 37% of employees report medium risk in the margin of action and control, highlighting the need to implement policies that provide greater autonomy and decision-making capacity to employees. Regarding recovery, 24% perceive inadequacies in break times, which could lead to progressive exhaustion if not adequately addressed.

Statistical analysis reveals a significant relationship between various psychosocial factors and job performance, with the margin of action and control standing out as the most influential factor (OR = 125). Furthermore, factors such as leadership and work organization also have a significant impact, reinforcing the idea that a well-led and organized work environment is key to maintaining a high level of productivity.

Founding

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